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**Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for CAIRT product
L2b overview**

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<i>Abstract</i> This ATBD describes the processing and generation of L2b products. In particular, the estimation of gravity wave (GW) perturbations and subsequent analysis and the estimation of age-of-air (AoA) from CAIRT trace-gas observations is documented. This document is meant as an overview of the technical processing and data description for these three products. For a more in-depth look into the method choice and description, refer to the accompanying technical papers. This ATBD describes all technical details on usage, configuration, and data structure.		
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1 Overview

This ATBD describes the processing and generation of L2b products. In particular, the estimation of gravity wave (GW) perturbations and subsequent analysis and the estimation of age-of-air (AoA) from CAIRT trace-gas observations is documented. This document is meant as an overview of the technical processing and data description for these three products. For a more in-depth look into the method choice and description, refer to the accompanying technical papers. This ATBD describes all technical details on usage, configuration, and data structure.

Each of the following corresponds to one of the three technical paper: Sec. 2 describes the GW analysis detailed in D-04-03a, Sec. 3 corresponds to the global-scale background estimation presented in D-04-03b, and Sec. 4 gives the technical description of the age-of-air estimation given in D-04-03c.

1.1 GW wave analysis: two-step approach

There is a whole zoo of different wave types in the atmosphere. They may be classified by the main restoring force of the wave. An overview of the most important wave types is given in Fig 1. Based on different forces, they accordingly have different dispersion and polarization relations and interact in different ways with the background atmosphere. Therefore we want to consider them separately. The practical problem then is to separate these individual wave types in observational data. This problem is non-trivial since observations do only provide a selection of variables (in our case temperatures) and are restricted in location and time. The different wave modes hence have to be separated via their scales. The problem is further complicated since all of these waves tend to have overlapping ranges of vertical wavelengths. The separation into different modes is important since the determination of GW parameters is deteriorated, if the wave analysis tool is applied on a data set containing other signatures than GWs.

Figure 1: Overview of the relevant restoring forces pressure, buoyancy, and Coriolis force and the main atmospheric wave types associated with them.

Separation of GWs from Kelvin waves and Rossby waves is possible via the global nature of these waves, tides have, in addition, a very distinct period (integer fractions of one day) which is sampled in a very peculiar way by a sun-synchronous LEO. Therefore, we need a dedicated tool for the scale separation, making use of the full global field provided by the satellite observations. Analyzing the resulting mesoscale structures associated with the GWs is then performed in a separate analysis tool, which performs the mesoscale wave decomposition, the calculation of GW

physical parameters and the change of the frame of reference from intrinsic to ground based for the phase velocity (Fig 2).

Figure 2: The whole chain of GW analysis consisting of scale separation, 3D wave decomposition and GW calculation

In this report we separate the two steps into two dedicated sections which are supported by a respective technical publication. Note that the global background estimation and the 3D wave analysis are both separate processes with a clear and lean interface data set and could be exchanged by a different method, if desired, without direct consequences for the other.

2 JUWAVE/S3D analysis

The gravity wave (GW) L2b product consists of wave parameters for individual wave events: the wave vector, amplitude, and phase are fitted from the input L2 temperature retrieval data (Table 1). Inferred parameters include the GW momentum flux (GWMF) and intrinsic phase speed. Calculation of ground-based phase speeds require auxiliary data in terms of winds, e.g., from a data assimilation system. GWMF and its vertical derivative (commonly called GW drag) are crucial in understanding the atmospheric circulation and thus the basis for SO-2.

There are many techniques for wave analysis in three-dimensional data. However, not all of them are similarly suited for the estimation of GWs on an orbit data grid, as needed for CAIRT. The most straightforward approach to detecting waves would be a Fourier Transform (FT) or the spatially limited windowed Fourier Transform. Both have a high spectral resolution but are limited in the spatial domain. In particular, the spectral content is assumed to have the same amplitude throughout the analysis interval and the periodicity of the wave fluctuations is necessary for accurate results. Both are not given for atmospheric GWs, which are spatially localized, and, in general, periodicity is not given for arbitrary analysis intervals.

A compromise between spectral and spatial resolution is given by wavelet analysis. Using wavelet functions, e.g., the Morlet wavelet, the fluctuations can be described locally at still relatively high spectral resolution, which is limited by the fact, that the wavelet functions for different spectral scales need to be orthogonal on a limited spatial region. These wavelets, however, still require a

consistent wavelength over a fairly large region and multiple wavelengths, which reduces the applicability for atmospheric GWs (Reichert et al., 2024; Ungermann and Reichert, 2025).

A method specifically tailored to detecting GWs in atmospheric parameters, such as wind and temperature fluctuations, is the finite-volume sinusoidal fit method in three dimensions (S3D; Lehmann et al., 2012, D-04-03a). It is based on the conception that in a specific region, a limited number of dominant wavelengths is present (e.g. Krisch et al., 2020). Accordingly, the amplitudes of finite cuboids of the atmosphere are scanned for a limited number of waves (also called wave components). By this physically-motivated limitation in spectral space, the resolution and localization in spectral space can be increased. As this method is tailored to atmospheric GWs and, beyond that, proven in many recent studies (e.g. Alexander et al., 2023; Geldenhuys et al., 2023; Krasauskas et al., 2023; de la Torre et al., 2023), this is the method of choice for generating the L2b product of GW parameters and subsequent GWMF and GW drag. The relation of S3D to other 3D wave analysis methods is discussed in D-04-03a.

2.1 Detailed method and algorithm description

The JUWAVE/S3D package consists of a number of individual programs for fitting, refitting and computation of inferred variables. For details, theoretical description, and assessment of the method, please refer to D-04-03a.

2.2 Description of the processing flow specific to CAIRT

For processing CAIRT data, the individual programs of the JUWAVE/S3D package need to be combined to an overall data flow and choices of parameters to be made. The L2b generation of GW quantities is therefore executed by three scripts and controlled by a common configuration file, which specifies the analysis parameters. The path to the scripts in the `cairt_scirec_gw` repository is `scripts/s3d_fitting`.

2.2.1 Overview

The three scripts are separated by stage of the processing and are dependent on the output of the previous script in the processing chain. As the sole input argument of these scripts, the name or path of a configuration `.toml` file may be given. The `.toml` file consistently initializes the parameters for the processing. If no argument is given, the default configuration file (`00_s3d_config.toml`) will be used. All scripts are set up such that specific steps are skipped if the corresponding output file is already present. The flow chart and dependencies are shown in Fig. 3. Note that the background removal is not part of the GW analysis but instead described in Sec. 3.

Figure 3: The retrieved, background-removed temperature data is processed to the L2b GW product using three separate scripts, which are configured via a .toml-configuration file. The background removal itself is described in Sec. 3.

2.2.1.1 S3D k-fit

The first step in the processing chain is the wave fitting of the retrieved temperature. This is done using the script `10_s3d_k_fit_cascade.py [config_file]`, which generates the S3D result file in the specified directory. The configuration file sets for which days, variables (typically only retrieved temperature), noise levels¹, and Nyquist penalty options S3D should be run. The background variable, which is subtracted from the variable to fit to have the residual perturbations only (in most cases this will be `T_BACKGROUND`), is of similar importance as the variable for the fit.

The main settings for the k-fit are the grid spec, i.e., the distribution of the analysis cubes along the orbit data and the sizes of these cubes. The cube size can be varied for different altitude regions, e.g., stratosphere, stratopause, and mesosphere, to tailor the analysis to the different GW properties in these regions: at increasing altitudes, GWs tend to have longer vertical wavelengths, which needs to be reflected by the vertical cube size. A result file will be written for each of the specified fitting domains. Furthermore, the number of different wave components and potential use of subcube cascade is specified here. These subcube cascades also reflect the larger vertical wavelength for higher altitude regions.

2.2.1.2 S3D refit of amplitude (and phase)

After the k-fit results for the different altitude regions have been generated, the amplitudes (and phases if needed) of the detected GW components are refit using the script `20_s3d_refit_cascade.py [config_file]`. Similarly to the k-fit, the refit will be performed for all specified days, k-fit variables, noise levels, and Nyquist penalty options. In addition, the refit can be run on different variables than the initial k-fit.

¹ The simulation of noise is part of the temperature E2E simulation and the noise specification has no influence on the processing steps within S3D. It is, however, part of the file name convention, so that we can easily exchange processing for different noise simulations

The main options for this refit are the method, i.e., amplitude or amplitude and phase, and the refit cuboid size. The cuboid size for the refit should be smaller than the initial cuboid sizes used for the k-fit for better localization of the GW amplitude. In particular, to take into account for strong changes in shear zones, a smaller vertical cuboid size is needed. and is fixed for all wave components. Furthermore, the refit could be performed in the opposite order of the k-fit.

A corresponding refit file is generated for each combination of k-fit file and refit variable.

2.2.1.3 Selection and Postprocessing

Based on the S3D k-fit and refit files, the third script, `30_selection_and_postprocessing.py` [config_file], performs various postprocessing steps. First of all, the result files of the specified altitude regions are combined into a single file containing the wave parameters for the full analysis region. Afterward, two different selections are performed. The first is based on the scale of the detected GW in comparison to the k-fit cuboid sizes: too short or too long wavelengths are flagged as unreliable. For the second selection, the k-fit and refit files are compared and GWs rejected that are inconsistent between both data sets. As a measure of this, the amplitude of the refit should not be vastly different from the one from the k-fit. The same is enforced for the phase if it was refit. The masks for both selection types are written out to a single file each. Name conventions are described below (see also Table 3).

Figure 4: Data flow and associated main JUWAVE programs as executed by the python scripts shown in Fig. 3

In order to estimate the GWMF from the GW parameters, the background temperature and density are needed. Therefore, one step of postprocessing is to add additional atmospheric parameters at the location of the k-fit cubes and infer additional variables. For this, the path to the grid atmospheric data needs to be specified. A S3D file containing all additional parameters and the background atmospheric values is written out. The selection masks generated in the previous step are added to this file for convenience. A fit is flagged as reliable only if both selections did so.

Finally, all parameters are present to calculate the GW drag, which is done by linearly interpolating the vertical gradient of GWMF along a specified amount of points, by default 5. The

option exists that a number of points in the height interval may be missing. By default, the minimum for the drag calculation are 3 existing data points, whereof at least one point needs to be above and below the considered altitude.

2.2.2 Configuration

The configuration of the GW L2b data generation is handled via a configuration file in the TOML language. This allows for Python-like argument initialization while keeping the configuration simple and easily adjustable. For using custom settings, all three scripts accept the path to a TOML configuration file as the sole argument. Thereby, multiple configurations can be saved for documentation and rerun at later points. If no argument is given, the default file, `00_s3d_config.toml`, will be used.

The settings are organized in tables corresponding to the stage that they configure. A full list of all settings including a brief description and example values is given in Table 1.

Table 1: List of all configuration variables present in the TOML configuration file for generating L2b GW data using the S3D tool.

Setting	Example Value	Description
io_settings		
<code>juwave_loc</code>	""	(optional) path to juwave installation, leave blank for user-specific installation
<code>main_path</code>	<code>"/cairt/2025/09/analysis/"</code>	absolute path to the base directory, where input and output are stored (in subdirectories)
<code>grid_atm_subdir</code>	<code>"nc"</code>	subdirectory in base dir with grid atmospheric data
<code>orbit_atm_subdir</code>	<code>"orbit_atm/"</code>	subdirectory in base dir with orbit atmosphere data
<code>orbit_atm_fname</code>	<code>"atm_rg_{}"</code>	filename without .nc ending and with as placeholder ({} for the time stamp)
<code>out_dir</code>	<code>"s3d_orbit_cascade6"</code>	subdirectory in base dir where results will be written
<code>log_dir</code>	""	directory for slurm logs, either relative or absolute
s3d_settings		
<code>alt_ranges</code>	<code>["stratosphere", "stratopause", "mesosphere"]</code>	specification of altitude ranges with potentially different cube-size settings
<code>x_grid_spec</code>	<code>[506.1, 151.83, 3800]</code>	along-track sampling of S3D cubes (in km; start, step size, number of steps)
<code>y_grid_spec</code>	<code>[-112.2, 99.75, 3]</code>	across-track sampling of S3D cubes (in km; start, step size, number of steps)
<code>bgr_T_var</code>	<code>"TEMP_BACKGROUND"</code>	variable that will be subtracted from the specified analysis variable before S3D is performed
s3d settings.alt grid spec		
<code>stratosphere</code>	<code>[15.0, 1.0, 20]</code>	entries have to agree with <code>alt_ranges</code>
<code>stratopause</code>	<code>[35.0, 1.0, 25]</code>	specification of the altitude S3D grid
<code>mesosphere</code>	<code>[60.0, 1.0, 21]</code>	(in km; start, step size, number of steps)
run_lists		
<code>kfit_var_list</code>	<code>["TEMP_RETRIEVED"]</code>	list of variables to perform the k-fit on
<code>refit_var_list</code>	<code>["TEMP_RETRIEVED"]</code>	list of variables to refit for all k-fit variables

daydoy_list	“[f’{i:02}_doy{i-1:03}’ for i in range(6, 8)]” or [“06_doy005”, “07_doy006”]	list of days to perform S3D on - either explicit list or Python-evaluable string. Fills placeholder in io_settings.orbit_atm_fname
k_fit		
max_remain_var	0.65	minimum fraction of the variance within the analysis cube that should be described by the wave fit before testing a second (slower) method
n_wave_comp	6	number of wave components that will be fit
ny_pen_ppt_height	8.0	height of the Nyquist penalty
ny_pen_ppt_width	0.8	width of the Nyquist penalty (in normalized spectral grid spacing)
slurm	true	enables/disables the use of slurm for the k-fit
k_fit.cube_size_pt		
stratosphere	[11, 9, 11]	(initial) cube sizes for the k-fit (in pt; along-track, across-track, vertical) specified for each altitude range separately
stratopause	[11, 9, 15]	
mesosphere	[11, 9, 19]	
k_fit.cascade_subcube_pt		
stratosphere	[2, 7, 9, 11, 4, 5, 7, 11]	cube size cascade specification for the k-fit (in pt; wave component, along-track, across-track, vertical) specified for each altitude range separately
stratopause	[2, 7, 9, 15, 4, 5, 7, 15]	
mesosphere	[2, 7, 9, 19, 4, 5, 7, 19]	
refit		
cube_size_pt	[5, 7, 5]	cube size of the refit cubes (in pt; along-track, across-track, vertical)
method	“amplitude_phase”	perform refit for amplitude only (amplitude) or amplitude and phase (amplitude_phase)
refit_cores	6	cores per job for the refitting (if using 25_refit_slurm.py)
selection		
lh_factor	3.0	maximum factor of wavelength to horizontal cube length that is still accepted
lz_factor	3.0	maximum factor of wavelength to vertical cube length that is still accepted
refit_ampl_ratio_range	[0.5, 4.0]	amplitude fraction of the refit amplitude to k-fit amplitude that is accepted
refit_max_phase_diff	60	phase mismatch between refit and k-fit that is accepted
drag		
linear_fit_pts	5	number of points on which the linear fit of GWMF is calculated for drag estimation
miss_pt	2	number of points that are allowed to be missing in the linear fit (has to be lower than the number of points for the fit)

2.2.3 Configuration implications

2.2.3.1 Refit selection criteria

the allowed range of amplitude and phase mismatch in the selection has a direct effect on the resulting spectra, making it necessary to choose these parameters wisely. Figure 5 shows the resulting spectra for different ranges for both parameters. It is evident that the major contribution to the spectrum stems from well-fitted GWs with low phase mismatch and an amplitude ration between 1 and 2. The edges of the considered parameter space contribute only slightly to the GW spectrum (central part) but in comparison stronger to the noise (upper right maximum). Therefore, in order to reduce the effect of not well fitted GWs, a sensible choice for selecting valid GWs is an amplitude ratio is 0.5 and 3 and a phase mismatch below 60 degree.

Figure 5: GW spectra for various selection criteria of the amplitude ratio (rows) and phase mismatches (columns) between initial k-fit and amplitude-phase refit. Dashed red lines show the edge, where the spectrum is cut in order to remove noise and parts of the spectrum that are unresolvable for CAIRT.

2.3 Data description

The following sections describe the input and output data sets. The description of the data structure is limited to the strictly needed variables. Refer to D-14 Readme-2 for a complete overview of the data structures.

2.3.1 Input data description

The input data necessary for the GW analysis using S3D is given in Table 1. In particular, this is the data that is generated by the background removal described in Sec. 3.

Table 2: Input data for the GW analysis via S3D.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	km	float32	altitude
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track		dimensionless	float32	track
TEMP_RESIDUAL	air temperature residual	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
latitude	latitude	degree_north	float32	time, track, altitude
longitude	longitude	degree_east	float32	time, track, altitude

2.3.2 Output data description

The data generated by the S3D GW analysis processing chain spans over different files containing results of different intermediate steps. An overview of their structure and naming is given in here.

2.3.2.1 File structure

The GW L2b data is generated as Network Common Data Form Version 4 (netCDF-4) files containing the wave parameters as well as inferred quantities and the background atmospheric values. Along the processing chain, some intermediate files are written. In the following, an overview of all generated files and the contained data is given.

All result files are written to the subdirectory `orbit_s3d_<out_dir_suffix>` in the specified main directory. For the k-fit and the refit, different files are generated. The root file names are constructed based on the configuration:

- `s3d_kfit_<kfit_var>_cs_<cs_x>x<cs_y>x<cs_z>_nph<ny_pen_height>_npw<ny_pen_width>_<orbit_atm_file_root>`

- s3d_refit_<refit_method>_<refit_var>
 cs<refit_cs_x>x<refit_cs_y>x<refit_cs_z>_kfit_<kfit_var>
 cs<cs_x>x<cs_y>x<cs_z>_nph<ny_pen_height>_npw<ny_pen_width>
 _<orbit_atm_file_root>

for the k-fit and refit files, respectively

The intermediate files written during the processing chain are labeled by a suffix to this base name. An overview of all generated files is given in Table 3. The final data file containing all information is given by the refit file base name with the suffix `_bgr_sel_drag.nc`.

Table 3: List of all intermediately written files during the GW L2b processing chain.

Filename suffix	Step #	Description
<code>_<alt_range>.nc</code>	1 & 2	k-fit & refit files for individual altitude ranges
<code>.nc</code>	3	& k-fit & refit files for all altitude ranges combined
<code>_selection.nc</code>	3	mask of reliable fits due to wavelength (k-fit) and amplitude/phase difference in the refit to the k-fit value (refit)
<code>_comp.nc</code>	3	& refit data with additional data comparing to the k-fit values
<code>_bgr.nc</code>	3	<code>_comp.nc</code> data with background atmosphere values and inferred variables added
<code>_bgr_sel.nc</code>	3	<code>_bgr.nc</code> data with selection of reliable fits
<code>_bgr_sel_drag.nc</code>	3	<code>_bgr_sel.nc</code> data with drag calculated from the GWMF

2.3.2.2 Output variables

The final output file containing all estimated parameters is the refit file with suffix `_bgr_sel_drag.nc`. A list of the main GW-specific variables provided in this file is shown in Table 4. For a full overview of the output data, refer to the technical document D-14 Readme-2. The dimensions are not spelt out for brevity. The abbreviations are as follows: alt: altitude, x: x coordinate, y: y coordinate, len gwmf: length of gwmf vector, len k: length of wave vector, wc: wave component.

Table 4: Most relevant output data and variables of the GW analysis. Refer to D-14 for a full overview of all output data.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions (abbreviated)
altitude	altitude	kilometer	float32	alt

time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00	float64	time
x_coordinate	projection_x_coordinate	kilometer	float32	x
y_coordinate	projection_y_coordinate	kilometer	float32	y
DRAG	drag as dF/dz from sum of all WC	m / s / day	float32	time, alt, y, x, len_gwmmf
DRAG_ALONG_WIND	drag in direction of wind	m / s / day	float32	time, alt, y, x
EASTNORTH_DRAG	drag from only eastward/northward waves	m / s / day	float32	time, alt, y, x, len_gwmmf
GWMF	pseudomomentum flux	Pa	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc, len_gwmmf
GWMF_ALONG_WIND	GWMF in direction of wind	Pa	float32	time, alt, y, x
K	wave vector; direction in local physical coordinates	1 / meter	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc, len_k
LATITUDE	latitude	degrees_north	float32	time, alt, y, x
LONGITUDE	longitude	degrees_east	float32	time, alt, y, x
OMEGA_GB	ground-based frequency	1 / second	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
OMEGA_INTR	intrinsic frequency	1 / second	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
PHASE	wave phase wrt cuboid center	radian	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
T_AMPLITUDE	temperature amplitude of fit	kelvin	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
WESTSOUTH_DRAG	drag from only westward/southward waves	m / s / day	float32	time, alt, y, x, len_gwmmf
LAM_H_err	error on horizontal wavelength	meter	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
LAM_Z_err	error on vertical wavelength	meter	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
ALPHA_err	error on wave direction	degree	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
T_AMPLITUDE_err	error on the temperature amplitude	kelvin	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc
GWMF_err	error on the pseudomomentum flux	Pa	float32	time, alt, y, x, wc, len_gwmmf

3 Temperature background removal for GW estimation

This section describes the generation of a physically meaningful background temperature field from observed planetary wave (PW) perturbations. By subtraction of this background from the direct temperature observations, small-scale GW perturbations are isolated for further analysis. The following sections describe the method choice and technical implementation, while the mathematical description and testing are shown in D-04-03b.

3.1 Method overview and choice

There are multiple different approaches for determining the GW fluctuations from temperature observations. The general approach is to estimate a large-scale temperature background that can be subtracted from the measurements. Afterward, the residual temperature should contain only small-scale perturbations, which, in the middle atmosphere, can be interpreted as GWs. The methods for generating the large-scale background can be divided in global and local approaches. In case of the global background estimation, planetary waves of wave numbers up to a cutoff wave number are considered to represent the temperature background. Strube et al. (2020), for example, estimated that zonal wave numbers higher than 18 can be taken as GW fluctuations in the stratosphere. Local background removal techniques, on the other hand, smooth the temperature field locally without specific knowledge of the planetary wave content. The smoothing can be done, for example, by application of a Savitzky-Golay filter to the measurement data (e.g. Linder et al., 2024). An overview of various methods for the background estimation is given in Sakib and Yigit (2022).

For observations with limited global coverage like, e.g., airborne or ground-based measurements, the estimation of planetary waves is impossible due to the lack of data. Thus, the local background estimation is the only possibility. These include cutting Fourier spectra at fixed scales (Krasauskas et al., 2023), linear and polynomial fitting in time and space for lidar measurements (Ehard et al., 2015; Reichert et al., 2019), and windowed spectral analysis of vertical profiles for satellite data (Ern et al., 2016).

Satellite data, on the other hand, open up the possibility for global scale background estimation. However, their limited sampling along the orbits reduce the maximum resolved zonal wave numbers and frequencies. The challenges posed by limited data at varying locations and times, inherent to satellite observation techniques, have been extensively described by Salby (1982). The impact of orbit precession on resolved maximum frequencies and wave numbers has been examined, highlighting that due to precession and limited daily orbits, shorter-period waves can leak into the observed zonal wave numbers.

Furthermore, very fast waves, e.g., (semi-)diurnal tides, could potentially be aliased to higher wave numbers; thereby ending up in the small-scale fluctuations interpreted as GWs. However, this problem is mostly relevant only at higher altitudes as the mesosphere, lower (MLT) thermosphere region. Therefore, it can be better to perform local background estimation in these special cases, as done by Linder et al. (2024).

A common method for global background estimation of the (static) PW content of measurements or model data is the use of the fast Fourier transform (FFT). This requires binning observed temperatures into a regular grid before applying the FFT, which simplifies the estimation of PW

coefficients but at the cost of losing knowledge of the exact measurement locations due to the binning process. Iwao and Hirooka (2021) provides an example of using FFT for PW estimation. However, the irregular sampling along longitude and the simultaneous progression of time render this approach unsuitable for applications requiring a precise, time-dependent PW background.

Lomb (1976) introduced an algorithm for precise spectral amplitude estimation from irregularly sampled data points. This method was refined by Scargle (1982) and is now known as the Lomb-Scargle method. It uses a least-squares approach to fit different wave components to observations and has been successfully applied to estimate gravity wave (GW) fluctuations in satellite data (Yamashita et al., 2013; Thurairajah et al., 2014; Ern et al., 2018; France et al., 2023). Furthermore, this approach yields the global planetary wave content for further research as a byproduct.

Given the proven effectiveness of the Lomb-Scargle method and its capability for time-dependent fits directly on non-regular observation locations and the physics-based approach of the fitting of planetary waves, we employ this method for the background estimation for the CAIRT studies.

3.2 Method and algorithm description

Figure 6 gives an overview of the steps of the different steps of the algorithm for the estimation of planetary wave (PW) spectra and the construction of a large-scale background. The input time series of temperature observations have to be interpolated to a grid in fixed latitude such that we can perform a wave scale analysis in latitude bands. The interpolation is needed in longitude and time along each orbit track. Next, a linear fit in time is subtracted from the interpolated data to remove any seasonal cycles and trends that might occur in the chosen time series. In particular, this is necessary because we aim to use 31 days of observations as the analysis windows.

Based on the latitude-interpolated and detrended data, the PW spectra are derived by fitting sinusoidal functions in longitude and time at each altitude and latitude. The maximum resolved zonal wave number is limited by the number of orbits per day and is estimated to be around 6, while the number of periods is limited by the length of the observation window. For the targeted data windows of 31 days, the methodology could resolve 31 different periods from 0 up to 30 cycles per 31 days. The resulting spectral components may be preprocessed, e.g., by removing specific parts of the spectrum, before a smoothing of PW components in latitude and altitude is performed. The smoothing ensures that the spectrum contains only PWs and no other fluctuations, whose amplitudes might vary strongly with latitude (e.g., large, northward-oriented GWs close to the poles).

Figure 6: Flow chart depicting the general algorithm for the separation of planetary wave scales from CAIRT measurements.

3.2.1 Latitude interpolation

For the Lomb-Scargle approach of estimating the planetary wave content, the input temperature data has to be analysed along full circles of latitude. As the satellite measurements are given on irregular sampling profiles in longitude and latitude, they have to be preprocessed. This can, for example, be achieved by binning the measurements in bands of latitude. Here, we linearly interpolate the temperature measurements along the orbit track to a fixed latitude grid. In particular, we interpolate also the longitude position of the measurement along-track for a more precise temperature distribution for the Lomb-Scargle fit.

The interpolation to the latitude grid is performed for each measurement track separately after splitting the data in to individual (ascending and descending) orbit legs. This orbit separation is performed by splitting the data at the measurement with the highest/lowest latitude location. Afterward, the interpolated data are concatenated again and form the altitude-longitude-fixed (ALF) data set for global wave fit in the next step.

3.2.2 Lomb-Scargle wave fit

As depicted in Fig. 6, the fit of the wave components is performed on latitude-interpolated data. This allows to estimate PW coefficients individually for each altitude and latitude band, which allows for the observation of varying PW fields. The observations used for the PW fit are still on a irregular longitude sampling. This has an important implication for the fitting of wave modes: due to the irregular sampling the wave modes might not be strictly orthogonal to each other, which can lead to spurious amplitudes. For one, consider a single wave sampled irregularly such that the

mean is non-vanishing. If we fit the modes separately to the data, we would recover the original wave but also a spurious offset due to the non-vanishing mean. To circumvent this problem, we use a simultaneous fit of all wave modes that we are interested in.

In particular, we solve the linear equation system

$$A\vec{c} = \vec{y},$$

where \vec{y} are the observed temperatures along the fixed latitude and altitude band and \vec{c} are the coefficients of the individual wave modes, which are described as $c_c \cos(kx - \omega t) + c_s \sin(kx - \omega t)$ with longitudes x , times t , wave number k , and frequency ω . The coefficient matrix A has dimensionality $N \times M$, where N is the number of sampling points and M is the number of parameters (twice the number of wave modes plus one) and is constructed as follows:

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & j = 0 \\ \cos(k_{n_j} x_i - \omega_{n_j} t_i) & j \text{ is odd} \\ \sin(k_{n_j} x_i - \omega_{n_j} t_i) & j \text{ is even } \wedge j > 0 \end{cases},$$

where the index of the wave mode is given as $n_j = \lfloor \frac{j-1}{2} \rfloor$. Solving this linear equation system gives the mean and amplitudes c_c and c_s for all wave components simultaneously preventing spuriously introduced amplitudes due to the sampling.

3.3 Processing description

The global wave fitting is implemented as a Python package. The generation of PW spectra and the large-scale backgrounds is driven by CLI scripts that are installed with the package. There are two main scripts in the package: one for generating the PW spectra and one for taking the spectra and generating the global scale wave field to the input temperature files. There is also the possibility to add the large-scale field directly to the input data after the spectrum is generated. The flow of these scripts is shown in Fig. 7. Details of the usage are given below.

Figure 7: Flow chart depicting the general usage of the global wave fitting package.

3.3.1.1 glofi_pw_decomposition.py

This script is used for the generation of PW spectra. In general, the input data should cover a period of about 7 to 28 days for a sufficient resolution of the time-dependent wave modes. An overview of the arguments and options of the script is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Arguments of the PW spectrum generating script `glofi_pw_decomposition.py`.

Argument	Description
<code>fns</code>	input data file names (including absolute or relative path)
<code>-h, --help</code>	show help message on script usage
<code>--pw_out_fn, -o</code>	file name to which the PW spectrum will be stored
<code>--data_type</code>	type of the input data (currently only 'cairt' is supported)
<code>--zwn</code>	maximum ZWM that will be fit for the PW spectrum
<code>--frequencies</code>	frequencies that will be fit for the PW spectrum (by default only constant wave modes are fitted)
<code>--frequency_unit</code>	unit in which the frequencies are given, by default 1/d
<code>--polysmooth</code>	apply smoothing across the PW spectra
<code>--ysmooth</code>	specification of the Savitzky-Golay filter applied in meridional direction (number of points, poly)
<code>--zsmooth</code>	specification of the Savitzky-Golay filter applied in vertical direction (number of points, poly)
<code>--n_interpolation_lat</code>	number of points for the intermediate latitude interpolation, by default 361
<code>--separate_orbits_by_track</code>	if given, orbit segments are separated for individual tracks
<code>--logfile, l</code>	path to the logfile
<code>--debug</code>	enable debugging messages
<code>--version</code>	display the version of the package

3.3.1.2 `glofi_add_bgr_from_spectrum_to_orbit.py`

This script takes a previously generated spectrum and reconstructs a large-scale background from the coefficients on the orbit data grid. The so-generated background accounts for the time of observation during the evaluation of the spectra. The overview of all arguments and options of this script is given in Table 6.

Table 6: Arguments of the spectrum-evaluating script `glofi_add_bgr_from_spectrum_to_orbit.py`, which results in the large-scale background field on the observation grid.

Argument	Description
<code>orbit_datafile</code>	File containing the observation grid (absolute or relative path)
<code>pw_coeff_datafile</code>	File containing the PW spectrum (absolute or relative path)
<code>-h, --help</code>	Show help message on script usage
<code>--variable, -v</code>	Name of the written-out background variable
<code>--data_type</code>	Type of the input data (currently only 'cairt' is supported)
<code>--spectrum_reference_date</code>	Reference date and time for the relative time to the spectrum generation date as ISO-formatted string
<code>--logfile, l</code>	Path to the logfile
<code>--debug</code>	Enable debugging messages
<code>--version</code>	Display the version of the package

3.4 Input and output data description

3.4.1 Input

The sole input data necessary for the global wave fitting and background generation is the temperature on the retrieval grid. The list of required input data is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Input data for the PW spectral analysis and background generation.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	km	float32	altitude
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track		dimensionless	float32	track
TEMP	retrieved air temperature	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
latitude	latitude	degree_north	float32	time, track, altitude
longitude	longitude	degree_east	float32	time, track, altitude

3.4.2 Output

There are two sets of output data generated from the global wave fit: the spectrum of planetary waves, represented by their amplitudes and phases, and the large-scale temperature background reconstructed from the spectrum on the CAIRT retrieval grid.

3.4.2.1 PW spectra

The spectrum of planetary waves can be written as a NetCDF file with entries as described in Table 8.

Table 8: Dimensions and variables of the planetary wave spectra.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	kilometer	float32	altitude
freq	frequency	1 / day	float32	freq
latitude	latitude	degree	float32	latitude
zwn	zonal wavenumber	dimensionless	float32	zwn
pw_amp	spectral amplitude	kelvin	float32	altitude, latitude, zwn, freq
pw_phase	spectral phase	radian	float32	altitude, latitude, zwn, freq

3.4.2.2 Large-scale temperature background

In order to isolate GW perturbations, a large-scale background reconstructed from the PW spectrum is generated by the global wave fit and (optionally) appended to the input file containing the full retrieved temperature field. Subtracting the large-scale background from the full temperature observations gives the isolated GW perturbations used by the GW analysis of Sec. 2. The added variable is described in Table 9.

Table 9: Dimensions and variables of the generated large-scale temperature background.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	km	float32	altitude
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track		dimensionless	float32	track
TEMP_BACKGROUND	retrieved air temperature	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude

3.5 Testing strategy

The testing strategy for the global-scale background generation and the estimation of planetary wave spectra is shown in Fig. 8. The foundation of the testing is high-resolution model data given on hourly time-steps. The data is scale separated using standard techniques (e.g., Strube et al., 2020) and large-scale spectra are generated using discrete space-time Fourier transform (FT) on the large-scale part. From these spectra, we generate a consistent time-dependent background state on the CAIRT retrieval grid. Combined with daily snapshots of GW perturbations (the small-scale part of a single model time step), this gives a consistent testing data set for the global wave fitting processing. The combination of a GW snapshot with time-varying background information is necessary because the model data is too coarse in time to represent the time dependence of the GWs (order of minutes).

The above-described methodology and processing is applied to the testing data set and we end up with three possible points of comparison:

1. PW spectra (compared against the FT spectra of the model data)
2. large-scale temperature background on orbit grid (compared against the FT spectrum sampled on the CAIRT orbit)
3. GW perturbations on orbit grid (compared against GW fluctuations of the model data)

Comparing all three of these quantities gives an estimation of the quality of the PW estimation methodology developed for CAIRT and the associated scale-separation.

The uncertainty on the resulting residual temperature is mostly determined by the uncertainty of the observed temperature. Due to the high latitudinal coverage of CAIRT, the uncertainty of the background temperature is much lower than the uncertainty of the observations and can be neglected in a first estimation. Note that the process of background generation is non-linear and the error such that a simple error propagation is not possible.

Figure 8: Testing strategy for the global-scale temperature background generation methodology. In particular, the red diamonds show where comparisons of the methodology with input data is performed.

4 Age of Air

The Age of Air (AoA) L2b product will be derived from the L2 retrievals of six trace gases: SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CH₄, and N₂O, at each point of the retrieval grid. This derivation will employ the innovative method proposed by Voet et al. (2025, D-04-03c), for which a preprint is currently available. Their study extensively discusses the advantages of this approach for remote sensing instruments like CAIRT, comparing it favorably to conventional AoA inference methods. The algorithm’s scientific foundation is comprehensively presented, offering a detailed description and justification for each step, both in mathematical and functional terms. Additionally, the study includes a thorough uncertainty analysis, providing a robust framework for the AoA L2b product generation. Figure 9 depicts a flow diagram of the method proposed by Voet et al. (2025, D-04-03c) that will be employed to derive the AoA L2b product.

Note that the generation of a zonal mean and of the look-up-tables requires some amount of data and cannot be done for individual orbits. However, CAIRT has sufficient coverage that these can be determined on a daily basis such that AoA can also be derived on a near real-time basis.

Figure 9: Flow chart depicting the general method for the inference of the AoA L2b product from the L2 retrievals of six trace gases SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CH₄, and N₂O.

4.1 Processing & input/output data description

Figure 10 depicts a flow diagram for each step of the algorithm that constitutes the method proposed by Voet et al. (2025, D-04-03c). The input data consists of the CLaMS model output interpolated to the CAIRT measurement positions as described in Sec. 9 and Table 7 of D-14 Readme-2.

Figure 10: Flow chart depicting the each step of the algorithm for the inference of the AoA L2b product from the L2 retrievals of six trace gases SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CH₄, and N₂O.

In the first step, an input file for a give time period will be processed with the python routine `retrieval_grid_to_zonal_mean.py`. The routine bins the retrieval-grid points of the input file in latitude and altitude and calculates the mean mixing ratio, accuracy (i.e. how close the values are to the real value), and precision (i.e., how far the measurements spread) for each tracer and bin, resulting in zonal mean distributions. In addition to that, `retrieval_grid_to_zonal_mean.py` calculates the center-point in time of the period covered by the input data. These zonal-mean data sets will be saved in netCDF4 format with the structure depicted in Table 10. The zonal mean file will be given the same name as the input file, but with the additional label `_zm` appended.

Table 10: Data description of the output generated by the python routine `retrieval grid to zonal mean.py`. Here, Q is a placeholder for the 6 considered trace-gases with labels ‘CH4’, ‘F11’, ‘F12’, ‘F22’, ‘N20’, and ‘SF6’. Refer to D-14 Readme-2 for the full description of the data structure.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
alt	altitude	km	float32	altitude
lat	latitude	degree_north	float64	lat
time	average point in time of the time period covered by the input file	days since 2000-01-01	float64	time
Q	Trace gas Q volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, lat, alt

Qacc	Accuracy of trace gas Q volume mixing ratio	m^{**3}/m^{**3}	float32	time, lat, alt
Qprec	Precision of trace gas Q volume mixing ratio	m^{**3}/m^{**3}	float32	time, lat, alt

In the next step, the so-generated zonal-mean file processed with the python routine `add_standard_aoa_to_zm.py`, which calculates the mean age of air and its uncertainty from the zonal mean SF₆ mixing ratio at each point of the latitude/altitude grid with the standard method described by Garny et al. (2024b) and the SF₆ sink correction proposed by Garny et al. (2024a). `add_standard_aoa_to_zm.py` adds the thus-calculated AoA and corresponding uncertainty values as two additional variables (depicted in Table 11) to the existing zonal-mean file and changes the ending of the file name from `_zm.nc` to `_zm_stAoA.nc`.

Table 11: Two additional data variables added to the zonal mean file by the python routine `add_standard_aoa_to_zm.py`.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
stAoA	Zonal mean AoA calculated from SF6 with standard method and sink correction	years	float32	time, lat, alt
stAoAerr	Uncertainty of zonal mean AoA calculated from SF6 with standard method and sink correction	years	float32	time, lat, alt

The python routine `create_lookup_tables.py` generates a lookup table from the `_zm_stAoA.nc` file for each of the six trace gases with the method described by Voet et al. (2025, D-04-03c). The lookup tables are used to convert tracer mixing ratios with uncertainties into corresponding AoA values with uncertainties. Each of the six lookup tables will be saved as a csv file of three columns named "`tracer`"_lookup_table.csv (where "`tracer`" is a place holder for trace gas in question). A description of the data in the three columns is shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Description of the three columns of the lookup tables generated by the python routine `create_lookup_tables.py` (saved in a csv file).

mean of mixing ratio bin	mean AoA in mixing ratio bin	Standard deviation of AoA in mixing ratio bin (natural variability)
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Thereafter, the python routine `AoA_on_retrieval_grid.py` reads these lookup tables to apply the method described by and infer a AoA value with matching uncertainty for each trace gas individually at each point on the retrieval grid of the original input file (see Sec. 9 and Table 7 of D-14 Readme-2). Subsequently, the routine will calculate the uncertainty-weighted mean AoA value out of the individual AoA values and uncertainties at each point of the retrieval grid. The results will be saved by adding the data variables shown in Table 13 to the existing data structure of the input file and appending the label `_plus_AoA` to the file name.

Table 13: Data description of the output generated by the python routine `AoA_on_retrieval_grid.py`. Again, Q is a placeholder for the 6 trace-gas labels 'CH4', 'F11', 'F12', 'F22', 'N2O', and 'SF6'.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
alt	altitude	km	float32	altitude

time	time	days since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track	across-track dimension	1	float64	track
AoAQ	AoA from trace gas Q volume mixing ratio	years	float32	time, track, alt
AoAQerr	Uncertainty of AoA from trace gas Q volume mixing ratio	years	float32	time, lat, alt
weightedAoA	Uncertainty weighted mean AoA from all individual AoA and uncertainty values	years	float32	time, track, alt
weightedAoAerr	Uncertainty of uncertainty weighted mean AoA	years	float32	time, track, alt

4.2 Error propagation concept

The total measurement uncertainty of each trace gas consists of an accuracy error and a precision error at the considered point of the retrieval. The zonal averaging of the initial data will reduce the precision error of each tracer uncertainty in each latitude/altitude bin by a factor equal to the square root of the number of points being averaged. The accuracy error each tracer, however, will remain unchanged by the averaging. In the end, the error of each tracer will be mostly determined by its accuracy due to the averaging. This reduction in precision error (e.g., caused by random error) results in tight correlations without much spread between the mixing ratios that are required for the described methodology.

The uncertainty in AoA values calculated from zonal mean SF6 will be estimated by linear propagation of the total SF6 uncertainty and the estimated uncertainty of the two parameters for the sink correction proposed by Garny et al. (2024a). Likewise, the AoA values inferred from the tracer mixing ratios at the retrieval grid will be estimated via linear propagation of all influencing uncertainties.

Up to here, we considered only individual trace gas concentrations and, therefore, the error covariance has been neglected. Furthermore, the methodology acts on vertical profiles, which allows us to neglect correlations in the horizontal. For the construction of the uncertainty weighted average AoA, however, possible cross correlation between trace gas species become relevant. The final error on the weighted AoA will consider the dependencies of errors between the trace gases.

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